

His transliteration into modern Burmese character is : —

အတ္တိဝိသတိဝေပုဒါတြယျသမေတာဂတာပုဒ္ဓိယ

With this reading Mr. Louis Finot, who has been kind enough to give the subject his close attention, is dissatisfied ; but I will not here enter on the discussion which has now lasted some months, regarding the inscription, character by character. Suffice it to repeat that all European criticism can only be of a tentative nature till the Government of India in the Archaeological Department is able to provide scholars with facsimiles of Burmese inscriptions of different epochs for comparison.

Aksharas will be observed close to the heads of the different Buddha figures, on the right side of each. These are probably the initials of their names — ဝိ *Ti* for Tissa, or Tishya ; က *Ka* for Kakusandha, Kassapa, or another ; and so on.

B. — Ceylon.

Slabs from Amarāvati at Anurādhapura.

In the museum at Anurādhapura, Ceylon, lie three marble sculptures ; two having groups of figures, while the third is the lower portion of a flattened octagonal pillar bearing an inscription. All three appear to have been brought to Ceylon from the Amarāvati Stūpa, in India. At the first glance I identified them as Amarāvati marbles, and subsequent investigation has confirmed me in this opinion. By permission of Mr. Still of the Archæological Department I brought with me to England a small chip from the rough unsculptured back of one of the slabs (fig. 4 of the Plate), and submitted it, together with a fragment picked up by myself in 1877 during the excavations at Amarāvati, for examination at the Geological Museum in Jermyn Street and the Imperial Institute Laboratories in South Kensington. The question put in each case was whether the Anurādhapura chip was a piece of Ceylon marble, or was of similar formation to the material of which the Amarāvati chip was composed.

Dr. Flett of the Geological Museum was kind enough to make a very careful analysis of the stones, and he sent me his written opinion thereon, in the following terms : —

“The two specimens of crystalline limestone which you left with me are so exactly similar in microscopic section that there can be little doubt that they are from the same locality. Some minor differences may be noted, but none of any importance, and as these schistose limestones are rarely exactly the same, even in the same quarry, these differences may be disregarded. The rocks are both of a somewhat peculiar character ; they consist of the same mineral and in very much the same proportions, and their structures are identical.”

In answer to my question whether he thought it possible for these two stones to have come from different countries, or whether their similarity must be held conclusively to prove that both came from the Pālnāḍ formations, which supplied the material for the Amarāvati sculptures, Dr. Flett replied : —

“I may say that I should certainly consider it a remarkable coincidence if two crystallized limestones, similar in foliation and in the nature and proportions of accessory ingredients, should occur in two places so widely separated. If the rocks were of a more common type this would not be extraordinary, but this limestone is a rock with well-marked characters, such as are not at all likely to be repeated.”

Dr. Evans of the Imperial Institute entirely concurred in this view, pointing out that the marble of Ceylon is very coarsely crystalline, and of quite a different structure and formation to the compact laminated limestone of the Pālnāḍ.

Since, moreover, the sculpture on the slabs is of pure Amarāvati type, that on the right being especially noticeable as being one of the older and more rare designs, the conclusion seems inevitable that all these marbles had, at some period, been brought from Amarāvati to Anurādhapura; and the only problems that remain to be solved concern the history of the transfer and its approximate date.

Now the pillar-fragment bears an inscription in old Singhalese (not Pāli) in characters of an early period, and it is therefore almost certain that this pillar arrived in Ceylon before that inscription was engraved on it. It appears to be an edict of some kind. As to its date I placed it roughly as belonging to the early fourth century A. D., and Dr. Hultzsch and Dr. Fleet have expressed their agreement with this view. Mr. Wickremasinghe, however, thinks that it belongs to the latter half of the fourth or even the first half of the fifth century. I leave readers to form their own conclusions on this point, merely repeating that the slab seems certainly to have come from Amarāvati and to have been in Ceylon before it was engraved.

The inscription is of course only a portion of the whole, and we see only the ends of the lines. The tenon at foot, seen on the right side, makes this clear. It is the lower portion of a pillar which had the edict engraved along its length, and we may perhaps have here about one-third of the whole. Eight lines are very clear; the six on the injured side are mostly illegible, though here and there an *akshara* can be read. It is not yet quite certain which line on the slab is the first line of the inscription; but considering that the last line of the injured side seems to come to an end before the end of the stone is reached, while the fourth side of the slab is blank, it is more than probable that the upper line seen on *a* is the first line.

Here follows Mr. Wickramasinghe's transliteration, and such translations of words as he has found possible:—

Text.

a

- (1) ha paṭamaka³ avanaka vasaha pa(tu)kaya biku-sagana(ṭa)
- (2) (para)tirehi gatiya hamaṇana mata (puti taṭa vi)
- (3) maha avasahi gatiya hamaṇana ca sava saga
- (4) avanakaṭaya ca nana magini pavata
- (5) ka maga karavaya tuḍala tuḍalalaka ca (ṭotahi) la
- (6) cata paha(ṇahi) ca bikusagahi ca tumahi ca hacaṇevī

b

- (7) aṭa ja⁴ layitaka (po)ta ja paṇca maha avasahi ja ca
- (8) ṭa a(?)nucaca karanakeṇakana paḍi aluvaḍu karanaka

Notes.

Line 1. *Biku saga*, "the community of monks."

Line 2 may mean "the parents of monks who have gone abroad."

Line 3. "Of the monks who have entered the great monastery (*i. e.*, The Mahā Vihāra?) and the whole community of monks."

Line 4. *ca nana magini pavata* = (Skt.) *ca nāna mārgeṇa parvata*, "and by various ways the rock."⁵

³ Or *paḍamaka*.

⁵ The name *parvata* may be applied to one of the great brick *stūpas* (R. S.).

⁴ Or *ḍa*.

ANTIQUARIAN NOTES IN BURMA AND CEYLON.

Plate II.

1. Fragment of a pillar taken from Amarāvati to Anuradhapura, Ceylon, and there engraved with an inscription. First side.

2. The same, second side.

3

4

3, 4. Marble fragments of sculpture from the Amarāvati Tope, found at Anuradhapura, Ceylon.

Line 5. *maga karavaya* (*maga* = Skt. *mārga*), "having had a road made."

Line 6. "at the Chaitya rock, and in the community of monks, and in himself (?)."

Line 7. *Pañca maha avasahi* — "In the five great monasteries."

This inscribed pillar was, Mr. Still informed me, found in one of the ruined buildings known as monastery "L" in the Abhayagiri *enceinte*, south of the Pattālam — Trincomalee road. Its discovery is recorded by Mr. Bell on page 3 of his *Report* for 1893. Of the other two Amarāvati slabs, that bearing the older design (on the right of fig. 4 of the Plate), was found exactly underneath the raised platform on which stands the Thūpārāma Dagoba within the limits of the Mahā Vihāra; and the slab with the newer design (on the left of fig. 4) was found in a small building, half way between the Bô-tree and the Isurumunīya Rock Temple, south of the Lohaprāsāḍa or Brazen Palace, and also within the Mahā Vihāra limits.

The newer sculpture (on the left of fig. 4) has been badly worn by, apparently, the movement of stones in running water, and is thereby greatly injured. The older slab (on the right of fig. 4) belongs to a period some centuries earlier than the more artistic Amarāvati age. A specimen of this type is given by Fergusson in his *Tree and Serpent Worship*, Plate LXXVIII — 2, and the author points out that its reverse side had been utilized for one of the more modern and better sculptures of the inner face of the great Outer Rail, which, according to him, was erected in the 4th century A. D.⁶ Dr. Burgess differs from Fergusson as regards this date, and shews reason for supposing that the Outer Rail belongs to the latter part of the 2nd century A. D.⁷ But for present purpose this difference of opinion is of no consequence. It is sufficient that at the later of these two dates, *viz.*, the 4th century, sculptured slabs belonging to the *stūpa* may have been lying about, detached from the structure and capable of removal, whether their detachment had recently taken place or had occurred two centuries earlier.

The slabs may have come over merely as ballast in an ordinary trading ship, — the Telugas of the East Coast were certainly a sea-faring folk at that period, as we know from records, traditions, and coins of the Āndhra kings, — or they may have been brought over by Anurādhapura sculptors as models for workmen. There is another possible explanation connected with the Legend of the Tooth Relic, which at the risk of being thought extravagantly fanciful I venture to put forward.

The Singhalese Legend of the Tooth does not stand alone and unsupported, for we know from Fāh-Hiān that the Tooth was actually in Ceylon before A. D. 412 (I shall quote him later); and the fact of a flight from Kalinga early in the 4th century of a royal personage carrying a relic is sustained by the stories of other countries. The legend runs thus: —

The king of Kalinga, being hard pressed by his foes, entrusted the Tooth Relic of Buddha to his daughter Hēmamālā and commanded her to fly with it to Ceylon. She obeyed these commands, set sail, and was wrecked on the "Diamond Sands." From this place she afterwards again set sail, and arrived safely in Ceylon, where she handed over the Tooth to the king.

Two other legends support the truth of this story, though they differ in details. There is a legend in Burma that a princess of Kalinga called Mā Hlā brought a relic of Buddha from that country to Thatōn, then the capital of Lower Burma, about the year 318 A. D.,⁸ and the *Chronicles of Orissa* relate that when in 327 A. D. the Hūna⁹ Yavana Prince Rakta Bāhu invaded their

⁶ *Op. cit.* p. 220.

⁷ *Amarāvati and Jaggayyapēta Buddhist Stūpas*, p. 12.

⁸ *Tree and Serpent Worship*, p. 174 n. Fergusson quotes from a paper by St. John in a monthly periodical called the *Phoenix*, II. 182.

⁹ This name "Hūna" appears to be an anachronism, as the Hūna invaders were not in India at so early a date; but their power was so greatly felt when they did come that their name became synonymous in people's minds with any tribe of Yavanas.

country and conquered it, the king of Kalinga fled from his capital, carrying with him the image of Jagannâtha. So that we have three legends concerning the flight of a royal personage with a relic from Kalinga in the first half of the fourth century A. D. Commenting on this fact, Ferguson writes:—¹⁰ “This struggle for the Tooth-Relic, in or about the year 318, excited not only all India and Ceylon, but extended across the Bay of Bengal to the neighbourhood of Martaban, and probably even further east; *but centred, if I mistake not, at Amaravati.*”

The date given in the Singhalese chronicles for the arrival of the Tooth in Ceylon is the 9th year of the reign of king Siri Mēghavaṇṇa. We cannot as yet be quite certain as to the dates of the kings of Ceylon. Professor Kern fixes 302 A. D. as the first year of that sovereign.¹¹ Mr. Bell thinks it was 304. Working solely from the *Mahāvamsā* I made it 319. According as we take these three dates the 9th year would be either A. D. 311, 313 or 328.

There is nothing historically improbable in the Orissan assertion that an intrusive Yavana invasion overthrew the old royal family of Kalinga early in the fourth century, for at that period the Guptas were undoubtedly gaining the ascendancy over the Yavana Kshatrapas in the West, and the power of the latter was completely crushed by about A. D. 350. So that fugitive princes with a large following may well have pressed eastwards to the sea after some Gupta victory. Samudra Gupta claims to have himself conquered Pishtāpura on the east coast.

Fergusson shews good reason for his identification of the “Diamond Sands” with the shoals at the delta of the Kṛishṇâ, a territory subject to the king who ruled at Dhanyakakāṭa, or Amarāvati, about 60 miles up the river, where for countless centuries diamond mines have existed and been worked. If this royal princess, then, had been saved from shipwreck on the coast, it is natural to suppose that she would have been conveyed to the capital, and from thence have made a fresh start. Her second journey, that is, would have been direct from Amarāvati to Ceylon.

And moreover there was a special reason why king Siri Mēghavaṇṇa should have been anxious to secure for himself a valuable and important relic of Buddha. His father and predecessor Mahāsēna had played havoc with the orthodox Sthaviravâda fraternity at the Anurâdhapura Mahâ Vihâra. He had persecuted them or allowed their persecution, and had given all the weight of his authority and power to the support of the Mahâyâna monks of the Abhayagiri and other hostile establishments. He had built and endowed the Jētavana Vihâra and Stûpa for the schismatic sect of the Sâgalikas. In his reign the monks of the Mahâ Vihâra had been compelled to abandon their home and fly to distant tracts, their monastery had been abandoned and destroyed; while the Lohaprâsâḍa had been dismantled and the materials carried off to the Abhayagiri enclosure, where the king had utilized them in the construction of several halls. When Mēghavaṇṇa came to the throne he reversed this policy, reinstated the priests of the Mahâ Vihâra, rebuilt the Lohaprâsâḍa and the ruined *parivēṇas*, and restored to their lands the ousted monks. But he also endeavoured to recreate some unity of feeling amongst the Buddhists of all sects; and as a means to this end the opportune arrival of so splendid a relic as the Tooth of Buddha was of inestimable value, since this was an object which the monks of all denominations must necessarily join in worshipping. We are told in the *Mahāvamsā* that the king received the relic with all the honour it deserved, and organized a great Dâthâdhâtu Festival, commanding that the tooth should be annually carried in a splendid procession from its resting-place in the Mahâ Vihâra to the Abhayagiri monastery. In this way he united all sects in one celebration, and soothed the disturbed feelings of the Abhayagiri

¹⁰ *Op. cit.* 175 n.

¹¹ *Manual of Indian Buddhism (Grundriss)*, p. 124. It is possible that this date is derived from the statement in the *Râjavaliya* that Mēghavaṇṇa's predecessor Mahāsēna died in the 845th year after the Nirvâṇa, the Nirvâṇa date being taken as 543 (845—543 = 302). But, if so, it is of doubtful authority.

sectaries. One feature of this festival was the making of a road along which the procession was to pass. Fâh-Hiân has left a description of the ceremonial as he saw it in A. D. 412 :—¹²

“The tooth of Buddha is always brought forth in the middle of the third month. Ten days beforehand the king grandly caparisons a large elephant on which he mounts a man who can speak distinctly and is dressed in royal robes, to beat a large drum and make the following proclamation :— ‘ . . . Behold ! ten days after this Buddha’s tooth will be brought forth and taken to the Abhayagiri Vihâra. Let all and each, whether monks or laics, who wish to amass merit for themselves, *make the roads smooth and in good condition, grandly adorn the lanes and byways,* and provide abundant store of flowers and incense to be used as offerings to it.’ ”

He gives an account of the festival that year, and says that the tooth remained at the Abhayagiri monastery for ninety days and was then “returned to the *Vihâra* within in the city,” *i. e.*, the Mahâ Vihâra.

In the *Dâhavaṅṣa* (written towards the end of the 12th century in the reign of Parâkrama Bâhu) it is stated that king Siri Mēghavaṅṣa had “caused a record to be written” of the arrangements he had made for the due honouring of the Tooth Relic.

If, therefore, this inscription be of so early a date as the reign of Mēghavaṅṣa (he reigned 28 years in the first half of the fourth century) it is within the bounds of possibility that it may be a fragment of the very record referred to, — very appropriately engraved on a slab which may even itself have been brought to Ceylon with the Relic. This is, of course, merely a conjecture, and must be received as such. But the contents of the few portions of lines that remain seem to shew that it is an edict of some sort, possibly a royal edict. It refers to the several communities of monks as distinguished from the special community of the orthodox at the Mahâ Vihâra (Line 3). It mentions the making of a road (line 5), though it is of course possible that the *mârḡa* referred to may have been a spiritual path. And its allusion in line 7 to the “five great monasteries” seems to shew that its object included the whole Buddhist community at Anurâdhapura for some one purpose. Finally, in line 4, is a fragment of a passage which may refer to a procession making its way to a *parvata*, and it is just possible that this was a name given to the huge Abhayagiri Dagoba.

If, however, Mr. Wickremasinghe’s date is correct, the edict could not have belonged to the reign of king Mēghavaṅṣa, but must have been engraved in the reign of one of his successors. But I must observe that the disturbed condition of the country renders it probable that the edict belongs to a period earlier than the end of the fourth century.

At present no more definite conclusion can be arrived at than that the marbles came from Amarâvatî, though not necessarily together ; and that whatever may be the date of the inscription, the pillar was almost certainly at Anurâdhapura before it was engraved.

Whether I am right or wrong in my conjecture is a matter for future determination, but it certainly invests this fragment with considerable interest, and it is to be hoped that the remainder of the pillar may some day come to light. It might be searched for in the neighbourhood of the place where the present portion was found, *viz.*, in the Abhayagiri *enceinte*.

¹² Legge’s edition, p. 105.